

Temple of the Storm-God in Aleppo

By Albert Dietz, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München

Entry tags: Ancient Western Asia, Religious Group, Temple, Religious Place, Ancient Syrian Religion, Archaeological monument

This entry gives an overview of the architecture, history and importance of the temple of the Storm-God in Aleppo, Syria (see chronological table). The temple together with the city is first attested textually and archaeologically in the middle of the 3rd mill. BCE. At this time the Storm-God of Aleppo seems to be venerated in the bigger region of northern Syria already. In the Middle Bronze Age (ca. 2000-1600) the temple was in the capital of the powerful kingdom of Yamḥad, promoting the importance of the Storm-God, the head of the pantheon of Ḥalab and one of the highest in Syria. Even after the fall of this dynasty, his importance did not decline. First Mittani ruled over Aleppo but was then defeated by the Hittites, who established a secundogeniture in the city. The temple was renovated and the Storm-God had already been adopted into the Hittite pantheon and venerated. This prompted the continuing importance of the temple, the growing prominence of the Storm-God of Aleppo and the spread of his cult and its iconography. By this time the Storm-God of Aleppo was venerated from Ugarit to Nuzi and up to Ḥattuša, showcasing the importance of this local deity. In the Iron Age the information is more scarce, but we know of a king Taita renovating the temple in the 11th cent. BCE. The temple stayed the cultic centre in northern Syria throughout the 1st mill. BCE. Since all of the textual attestations of the temple and its daily life have been found in other cities, most things about the cult, the festivals and the rituals remain in the dark. Aleppo is one of the oldest cities that are permanently occupied and therefore excavations are very limited. The discovery of archives in Aleppo would contribute a lot to the history of the temple and the city. Only the rich decoration and ground plan of the temple remain today. The importance of the temple is secured by many letters, religious texts and offering lists from Syria, Anatolia and Northern Mesopotamia naming the local Storm-God of Aleppo. Due to his widespread importance and veneration the Storm-God can be called by different names, depending on the cultural background: Hadda, Addu, Teššub, Tarḫunta, Ba'al and Hadad. His unique iconography sets him apart from other Storm-God depictions.

Date Range: 2500 BCE - 500 BCE

Region: Aleppo

Region tags: Middle East, Syria

The Temple of the Storm-God is located on the citadel of the city of Aleppo. It has an entrance with two adjacent rooms and a cella (with a niche in the Middle Bronze Age).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Other [specify]: Citadel of the city of Aleppo

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The exterior of the temple could not be excavated because of the densely build citadel. The excavation border of the temple touches the Zangid mosque in the west; an Ayyubid palace in the south and a modern theatre in the east. This perfectly shows the long and multilayered history of the citadel. Because of the foundations of later buildings only limited informations about the inventory of the temple are known.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: It is unclear if everyone was allowed to enter the temple

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Notes: Since the area around the temple is unknown due to more recent buildings hindering excavations, we can only say that most of the temple is excavated.

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: This is hard to answer, since every ruler intended to create buildings showing his power, piety and influence for eternity.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Several times parts of the building and the architectural decoration were renovated or changed.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Notes: In antiquity the temple was destroyed by fire at least three times: after the rule of Hurri-Mittani over Aleppo when it was conquered by Suppiluliuma I.; after the end of Hittite rule; after the 10th century

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of war

– Other [specify]: Destroyed in Antiquity. The damages in recent years during the civil war remain unclear

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Storm-God of Aleppo (ancient Ḥalab, capital of the Kingdom of Yamḥad);

venerated as Hadda, Addu, Teššub, Tarḫunta, Ba'al and Hadad

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: Probably the deities that are connected to the Storm-God like his wife and his son might have been venerated as well.

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Kohlmeyer, Kay . The Temple of the Weather God of Aleppo. Münster: Rhema-Verlag, 2020.
- Source 2: Kohlmeyer, Kay. "The Temple of the Storm God in Aleppo during the Late Bronze and Early Iron Ages." *Near Eastern Archaeology* 72, no. 4 (December 2009). <https://doi.org/10.1086/nea25754027>.
- Source 3: Dietz, Albert. *Der Wettergott Im Bild. Diachrone Analyse Eines Altorientalischen Göttertypus Im 3. Und 2. Jahrtausend v. Chr., MAAO 8.* pp. 151-166. Gladbeck: PeWe-Verlag, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5282/edoc.32247>.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

- Mound
- Leveling of ground
- Terracing

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many divine beings (Mischwesen) are shown on the reliefs decorating the room, but it is not sure if these were also venerated.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.hittitemonuments.com/aleppo/>
- Source 1 Description: Homepage on the Hittites and the monuments connected to them. Many pictures of the temple and the hittite reliefs
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.wmf.org/project/temple-storm-god-citadel-aleppo>
- Source 2 Description: On the conservation of the temple in 2005. An envisioned Museum connected to the temple could not been realised because of the war.

– Source 3 URL: https://www.gerda-henkel-stiftung.de/en/die-zitadelle-von-aleppo-und-der-tempel-des-wettergottes?page_id=75709

– Source 3 Description: Report about the project funded by the Gerda Henkel Stiftung from 1996-2005 (in German)

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: In the 11th century BCE the king Taita of the Palistin renovated the temple and build the image of himself in relief next to the depiction of the storm-god (cult-image?) installed by the Hittites. The relief of the king must have replaced another depiction that is now lost.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:
– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:
– Year range: 1996-2010

↳ Name of excavation
– Official or descriptive name: Syrian-German excavation under the direction of Kay Kohlmeyer

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The first attestation of Halab (modern Aleppo) and their Storm-God was found in offering lists from Ebla dating to the 24th century BCE. By that time we have no texts from Halab and therefore can not say who build the original temple. In later periods we know of rulers renovating the temple, most famous, because he is still visible, is King Taita (11th cent. BCE; see above).

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know. No local texts about the temple and it's history are known.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

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– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Storm-God of Aleppo (ancient Ḫalab, capital of the Kingdom of Yamḥad); venerated as Hadda, Addu, Teššub, Tarḫunta, Ba'al and Hadad

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

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Notes: Probably the deities that are connected to the Storm-God like his wife and his son might have been venerated as well.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

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Notes: Many divine beings (Mischwesen) are shown on the reliefs decorating the room, but it is not sure if these were also venerated.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

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Notes: In the 11th century BCE the king Taita of the Palistin renovated the temple and build the image of himself in relief next to the depiction of the storm-god (cult-image?) installed by the Hittites. The relief of the king must have replaced another depiction that is now lost.

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Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know. No local texts about the temple and it's history are known.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Spanning the different stages of the temple over 50 relief blocks were found, some of them re-used and re-worked over time. At the entrance two lions and one sphinx partly worked out of a block that was used as the body. Limestone and basalt was used for the decoration.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Two depictions of the Storm-God of Aleppo and several minor gods; most of them cannot be identified by name, but because of their horned crown they clearly are divine.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Male and female sphinx', bull-men, fish genius, winged genii with different animal heads and other composite monsters ('Mischwesen')

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Old Syrian (Start of 2nd mill. BCE) reliefs and statue bases show depictions of humans, but they are very fragmentary and often re-used. The most prominent human is King Taita next to the Storm-God (see above).

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Lions and bulls. Alone or antithetically.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: see other supernatural beings

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: So called 'false windows' that are typical for Hittite temple architecture (maybe because in the Hittite heartland temples had more windows). The lattice can be decorated with coils and intertwined ribbons.

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: Although today parts of the decoration is barely visible because it is located under more recent buildings and some of it could only be revealed by tunnels, which is very dangerous and therefore very limited. But in antiquity all the decorations were visible for everyone with access to the temple.

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Notes: Several bases for statues have been found. Offering lists from Ebla (24th cent. BCE) mention a composite statue with lapis lazuli head and chariots as well as metal sheets for the decoration of statues. And there is a letter addressed to the King of Mari (Zimri-Lim; M.7161), found in Mari, talking about the statue of the Storm-God of Aleppo, and that the king wanted to erect a statue of himself in the temple (18th cent. BCE). Hittite King Hattuşili I. (1650-1620) took ('god-napped') the cult statue on his campaign against Syria. Therefore some secondary evidence about several statues that are nowadays lost exist.

↳ Cult statues:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some argue that the depiction of the Storm-God of Aleppo from the Hittite Period was the cult statue (or better: cult relief), which seems plausible but there is no final proof so far. The cult statue of the Storm-God is known from several texts, but not identified.

On the problem of cult statues in archaeology and the visual sources see Dietz 2019.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Two Lions and a sphinx partly hewn out of a block, parts of the body in high relief (more relief than statue).

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: See decoration figural

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

Notes: At least not apparently evident.

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: For the inscriptions in detail see Hawkins 2011.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Parts of the lion and the sphinx sculpture at the entrance carry inscriptions that are very fragmentary but seem to be historical (Hawkins 2011, ALEPPO 7).

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: The inscription around the figure of the king Taita (Slab ALEPPO 6) states his position and instructions for future sacrifice (see Hawkins 2011)

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Offeringlist from an archive in Ebla (24th cent. BCE) name several gifts: metal sheets for decorating statues, silver and fold plated bull horns and gold plated mace heads (see Archi 2010). This is only a small glimpse into the temple inventory of which only very little was found archaeologically.

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The depiction of the Storm-God of Aleppo is a rare example of a Storm-God with a distinctive way of depicting the deity. Normally only Storm-God types were depicted (see Dietz 2023). But the Storm-God of Aleppo has a depiction that can be traced over centuries over a vast geographical area (see Dietz 2019). He is depicted ascending his bull drawn (sometimes bird-shaped) chariot. At Aleppo this type of depiction is seen at the pedestal wall.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

|

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

Notes: Not found in situ but many temples were plastered with a calcareous paste to heighten the appearance of the temple.

↳ Wood
– No

Notes: Not found in the archaeological contexts but was probably used for the upper structures and possible upper floors.

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

Notes: Most probably. The two stones used for building and decorating were limestone and basalt. Limestone is abundant in the region of Aleppo, for the temple they might have used limestone quarried directly at the citadel (Kohlmeyer 2020, 49). 12-15 km south-east of Aleppo is an ancient quarry and a basalt field. Prepared basalt blocks found there resemble and match the size of the hittite reliefs in the temple. Also many sculptures in the temple were re-used. For the quarries and re-use see Kohlmeyer 2020

49-50.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:
– No

Is monumental architecture present:

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↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: For the inscriptions in detail see Hawkins 2011.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Parts of the lion and the sphinx sculpture at the entrance carry inscriptions that are very fragmentary but seem to be historical (Hawkins 2011, ALEPPO 7).

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: The inscription around the figure of the king Taita (Slab ALEPPO 6) states his position and instructions for future sacrifice (see Hawkins 2011)

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Offeringlist from an archive in Ebla (24th cent. BCE) name several gifts: metal sheets for decorating statues, silver and fold plated bull horns and gold plated mace heads (see Archi 2010). This is only a small glimpse into the temple inventory of which only very little was found archaeologically.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The depiction of the Storm-God of Aleppo is a rare example of a Storm-God with a distinctive way of depicting the deity. Normally only Storm-God types were depicted (see Dietz 2023). But the Storm-God of Aleppo has a depiction that can be traced over centuries over a vast geographical area (see Dietz 2019). He is depicted ascending his bull drawn (sometimes bird-shaped) chariot. At Aleppo this type of depiction is seen at the pedestal wall.

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Several letters from the king of Mari talk about journeys to the temple of the Storm-God. The word pilgrimage we use today might not be the correct one for this.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– I don't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– I don't know

Is divination present:
– I don't know

Is this place a tomb/burial:
– No

Do rituals occur at this place:
Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.
– No

Notes: No rituals are written down or are visible in the archaeological record.

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– No

Is a supreme high god is present:
– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– Yes

Notes: Can be.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– I don't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– No

Notes: Not to the enemies of the God and the king. And Storm-Gods can also bring disastrous storms and hail that can ruin crops.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:
– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:
– I don't know
Notes: Probably

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
– I don't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:
– No

Notes: Neither texts nor the archaeological record can support this.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Notes: From Ḫattuša (capital of the Hittites) we know of 13 festivals for the Storm God of Aleppo, who was also venerated in Ḫattuša. There are no further informations about these festivals. They might have a northern syrian origin, but we cannot take for granted that these festivals were present in Aleppo as well (Schwemer 2001, 496).

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: Informations about the cult statue are only known from written evidence. There might be a big limestone base/throne in the rubble of the temple that might have been used for a cult statue. The relief of the Storm-God of Aleppo at the eastern wall of the cella might have function as a cult image as well.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Notes: Can be.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– I don't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

Notes: Not to the enemies of the God and the king. And Storm-Gods can also bring disastrous storms and hail that can ruin crops.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Probably

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

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Notes: Informations about the cult statue are only known from written evidence. There might be a big limestone base/throne in the rubble of the temple that might have been used for a cult statue. The relief of the Storm-God of Aleppo at the eastern wall of the cella might have function as a cult image as well.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Notes: No rituals are written down or are visible in the archaeological record.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Several letters from the king of Mari talk about journeys to the temple of the Storm-God. The word pilgrimage we use today might not be the correct one for this.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– field doesn't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– I don't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Notes: Neither texts nor the archaeological record can support this.

Are festivals present:

– No

Notes: From Ḫattuša (capital of the Hittites) we know of 13 festivals for the Storm God of Aleppo, who was also venerated in Ḫattuša. There are no further informations about these festivals. They might have a northern syrian origin, but we cannot take for granted that these festivals were present in Aleppo as well (Schwemer 2001, 496).

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Notes: There is the inscription of King Taita on the relief slab depicting him. No archive was found.

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– Field doesn't know

Present part time

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: The importance of the Storm-God of Aleppo is mentioned in several external texts, but there is no specific scripture dealing with the temple.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Not in the excavated part of the temple area.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: The temple received offerings from all over northern Syria and beyond through the ages and therefore we can assume that it was also an important economic player in Aleppo, since temples in general were economic powers in Ancient West Asia.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Not in the excavated part of the temple area.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: The temple received offerings from all over northern Syria and beyond through the ages and therefore we can assume that it was also an important economic player in Aleppo, since temples in general were economic powers in Ancient West Asia.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Notes: There is the inscription of King Taita on the relief slab depicting him. No archive was found.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: The importance of the Storm-God of Aleppo is mentioned in several external texts, but there is no specific scripture dealing with the temple.

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